

BIO-TECHNOLOGY: Newer Biology -An Impression

(Jaydip Datta et al)

In this Impression a modern scope of bio-technology is discussed. The word Bio-Technology literally means a combinatorial hybrid of classical Biological - Science with some Chemical Industrial aspects. The micro biomes – the origin of this newer biology ie MICROBIOLOGY , MOLECULAR BIOLOGY , rDNA science , Virology (Most important biological entity – Corona Virus –Latest Global Issue !!!) . The recombination power of Microbial Kinetics including bacterial as well as Viral cloning to more powerful as well as Virulent type – This type of cloning is irreproducible very often as per Statistical Relevance – a Limitation of Genetic Engineering.

Keywords :

Newer biology , rDNA , Environmental biotechnology , SARS-COV-2 Structural dynamics, Antibiotic resistance , Neoplasm .

Discussion Reference :

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